

The Usability of Touch Screen interactions for Older Adults: a Systematic Review

Parisa Mousavi Mehr, Saeed Kanani, Thomas Lachmann, Ann-Kathrin Beck

Introduction

As touchscreen devices become a part of everyday life, it is important to understand how well they work for older adults who may face challenges such as reduced vision, slower motor skills, and less experience with digital interfaces (Nurgalieva et al., 2019). User experience (UX) plays a key role in shaping how usable and comfortable these devices are (Menghi et al., 2017). While some studies have explored usability issues by comparing older and younger users in testing different features, a quantitative review has yet to be conducted to study what works best. The purpose of this study is to perform a meta-analysis to address that gap by investigating how UX interaction impacts usability attributes in touchscreen devices used by older adults.

Inclusion criteria:

- Studies in the context of touchscreen interfaces.
- Studies published from 2015 to 2025.
- The study must include quantitative usability testing, such as (but not limited to):
 - System Usability Scale (SUS)
 - Task success rate
 - Time-on-task
 - Error rate
 - Satisfaction
 - Learnability
 - Acceptability
 - Ease of use
- quantitative results can be a comparison between older adults and younger adults

Exclusion criteria:

- Articles that are not written in English.
- Articles not dealing with touchscreen interfaces (e.g., mouse, keyboard, VR without touch interaction).
- Articles without a quantitative usability test. Qualitative research articles and literature reviews that do not perform a usability test with users are excluded.
- Articles not providing results for older adults, or cannot extract older adult data separately.
- Full-text articles are inaccessible.

Search Strategy:

The following search string will be used to capture relevant studies across databases. The search combines four key concepts: (1) older adults, (2) touchscreen, (3) apps, and (4) usability outcomes.

(elder* OR "aging population" OR senior* OR older) AND (touch OR "touchscreen" OR "touch screen" OR "touch interface" OR "gestur*") AND (usability OR "task completion" OR "success rate" OR "user performance" OR satisfaction OR "reaction time" OR accuracy OR "user preference" OR "error pattern") AND (mobile* OR app OR application OR *phone OR smartphone)

This search will be applied to the following databases: Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, and ACM Digital Library. Search strings will be adapted to match the syntax of each individual database.

References:

Menghi, R., Ceccacci, S., Gullà, F., Cavalieri, L., Germani, M., & Bevilacqua, R. (2017, September). How older people who have never used touchscreen technology interact with a tablet. In *IFIP Conference on Human-Computer Interaction* (pp. 117-131). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Nurgalieva, L., Laconich, J. J. J., Baez, M., Casati, F., & Marchese, M. (2019). A systematic literature review of research-derived touchscreen design guidelines for older adults. *IEEE Access*, 7, 22035-22058.